

PREDICTIVE MODEL AND ACCELERATED CHARACTERIZATION OF VISCOELASTIC RELAXATION IN BOLTED COMPOSITE JOINTS

J.X. Lv¹, Y. Xiao^{2*}, R.G. Pei³

^{1,2} School of Aerospace Engineering and Applied Mechanics, Tongji University, Shanghai 20092, China

(* E-mail: y_xiao@tongji.edu.cn)

³ AVIC Commercial Aircraft Engine Co.,Ltd, Shanghai 200241, China

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ABSTRACT

Structural joints are the most common part where durability problems occur due to its susceptibility to hydrothermal environment and mechanical load. Composite joints inevitably encounter all sorts of environmental ordeal especially exposure of hydrothermal nature in the process of actual operation. Two key problems were investigated in structural durability design for mechanically fastened CFRP joints: temperature-time dependent behaviour for the viscoelastic preload relaxation, and prediction method for its long-time performance. A new preload prediction model was developed and accelerated tests were designed and performed for characterizing the long-term relaxation. Comparison of model prediction and accelerated tests results is conducted to identify the present model's validity regarding bolted composite joints relaxation.

1 INTRODUCTION

A new phenomenological model for preload prediction was derived to predict bolted composite joints relaxation by using the creep total-strain theory^[1]. Compared with other relaxation models such as H-N model proposed by Hook and Norton derived through steady state creep^[2] and S-C model proposed by Shivakumar and Crews derived through transient creep state^[3], present model considered both two creep state and provided more accurate prediction consequently. For proving present model's validity and veracity, long-term relaxation of the joints was obtained through accelerated test method (hereinafter termed by ATM) based on the time-temperature-stress superposition principle^[4].

2 METHODOLOGY

A new approach was discussed to assess the long-term behavior of bolted composite joints under hydrothermal environment by combining an analytical model with accelerated tests.

Firstly, a relaxation predictive model was developed based on the creep total-strain theory. Normally creep of viscoelastic material includes two states: transient creep firstly and steady state secondly. Both states were considered and as a result the model is derived in Piecewise form written as Eq. (1). t^* represents the critical time when transient creep transfers into steady state creep. A, B, C in Eq.(1) are material parameters obtained through short-term (36h) tests. α_T in Eq.(1) is the time-temperature shift factor which can be obtained whether by short-term tests or by the time-temperature conversed relation. Study reviews that similar results are available through the two methods. Using this prediction model, the viscoelastic preload relaxation behavior for bolted joints at any period can be well described.

$$\frac{P_t}{P_0} = \begin{cases} 1 / \left[1 + \frac{A}{\alpha_T} t^B \right]^C & 0 < t \leq t^* \\ 1 / \left[1 + \frac{A}{\alpha_T} t^{*B} + \frac{ABt^{*B-1}}{\alpha_T} (t - t^*) \right]^C & t \geq t^* \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Secondly, comparison with present model and the other two typical bolt relaxation models revealed a little difference in between regarding results of long-term relaxation (like 20 years). Discussion was conducted on why these differences arose and which one is the most adaptive model.

Thirdly, for identifying the most realistic model, accelerated tests based on time-temperature-stress superposition principle were designed and performed for characterizing long-term relaxation which can be represented as a master curve showed in Figure 1. Then, by comparing the master curve and three different model prediction curves showed in Figure 2, the prediction curve closer to the master curve was considered as the more realistic one.

3 RESULTS

Part of ATM results are showed in Figure (1). Figure (2) presents the comparison of long-term model predictions (included present model and other models) and ATM results.

Figure 1: Master curve of composite material connection in room temperature (25°C).

Figure 2: Different model prediction curve and ATM results.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Comparison of accelerated test results and model prediction shows that they agree very well to each other and that therefore the model is valid for long-term relaxation prediction.

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